

Deliverable D4.2

Guidance document for the implementation of a standardized pre-analytic workflow in selected fields

Annex

Work package number and title	<i>WP4 Standardization and Quality Control</i>
Work package leader	<i>MUG</i>
Relevant Task	<i>T4.2</i>
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Other contributors to Deliverable	<i>AIT, CABI, INRAE, HMGU, DMSZ, EMBL, SU</i>
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Pre-analytical variables and metadata relevant for plant microbiome studies

Pre-Analytic Phase - Key Steps	Key Pre-Analytical Variables & Details	
IN SITU - pre-analytical effects on specimens/samples		
Pre-Collection	<u>ENVIRONMENT / HABITAT / PLANT</u>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Location / site / habitat</u> 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Geographic: e.g. latitude, longitude & altitude 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Type of environment e.g. natural (e.g. managed field, native environment/nature) vs artificial (greenhouse, laboratory, seed bank) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Type of ecosystem (e.g. grassland, desert, forest, wetland, mountain) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Biodiversity on sampling site (e.g. richness of plant community) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Agricultural & plant management practices e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fertilization/nutrient addition - pesticide application - watering - management history (e.g. cropping history, agricultural management before current plant rotation) - mowing/grazing (machines/animals) 	H H
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>External condition history (before collection)</u> 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Climate (e.g. alpine, Mediterranean, tropical) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Former weather conditions (e.g. precipitation - amount and the type of rainfall) temperature; drought) 	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Plant</u> 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Plant species / genotype 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Mother plant / genotype 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Plant age and/or developmental stage (life cycle such as seed storage, emergence, growth, flowering, fruit development, maturity, ripening, senescence, and decomposition) 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Phytosanitary status (plant health/disease status) e.g. healthy diseased, type of disease, severity (area/volume of plant tissue relative to total plant) 	H	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Root extrudate 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Legally and regulatory relevant documents</u> (e.g. Nagoya-relevant documents, phytosanitary permits, customs declaration, export/import documents) 	H	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Soil (breeding ground):</u> Soil parameters e.g.: 		

○ Physical properties (e.g. soil type, texture class, structure)	
○ Chemical properties (e.g. pH, N, P, K; organic carbon and other matter; dry matter, micronutrients, other (electrical conductivity, cation exchange capacity))	H
○ Biological properties (e.g. microbial biomass, potential enzyme activities (if available))	H

EX SITU pre-analytical effects on specimens/samples

Sampling/ collection

SAMPLING / COLLECTION

● Sampling site/area/design (incl. habitat & sample heterogeneity)

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|--|---|
| ○ Degree of heterogeneity at sampling area, size of sampling area, design/distribution of sampling (e.g. stratified sampling e.g. in quadrants or random sampling) | H |
| ○ Soil at plant collection site (particularly for rhizosphere microbiome analysis), e.g. physical properties (such as texture/density, structure/porosity/aggregate size) | H |

● Sampling method/procedure

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|---|---|
| ○ Sampling method/procedure | H |
| ○ Sampling equipment/instrument(s)
(e.g. for associated soil: soil core collectors, sterilized sieve, for plants: shovels [e.g. for digging up plants], scissors and/or shears [e.g. for cutting plant roots, leaves], trays, cutting board, knives, bags, containers; gloves; | |
| ○ Sample/plant compartment
(e.g. root, leaf, seed, ...) and the exact site/part within a compartment (e.g. different root parts near surface or root tip) | H |
| ○ Separation of compartments (in the field versus in the lab) | |
| ○ Cleaning of the sample (if relevant) in the field vs in the lab and by which cleaning methods (e.g. for removal of soil and/or rhizosphere): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Dry methods (e.g. scraping off with disposable spatulas, shaking roots, or removed with gloved hand); – Wet methods (e.g. washing of soil e.g. by soft methods like agitating root in sterile liquid to remove adherent soil and microbes, or shaking/agitating, or by harsher methods: vortexing or sonication in buffers with/without detergents); – Mechanical separation methods (e.g. removal of the coating from the seeds for endophyte microbiome analysis) | |
| ○ Sample fractionation, subsampling vs pooling
e.g. full root vs root tip, multiple leaves or entire single leaf or parts of a single leaf (is it destructive method e.g. cutting a root which release endophytes or be contaminated with rhizosphere, or not) | H |

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sampling date/time (schedule) (e.g. time important when sampling last the entire day and for circadian rhythm; data: indicator of season) ○ Weather conditions at time of collection (e.g. precipitation - amount and the type of rainfall; temperature) ○ Control samples (i.e. sampling of environmental controls like soil, rhizosphere, root extrudate where needed) ○ Sample container(s) type, condition, label(ling) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – <u>Container type and condition</u>: (e.g., closure integrity, material resistance to temp./chemicals size (for holding sample & preservation solution) evaporation or spillage, breakage, leaking; – <u>Labelling</u> (unique ID linked to information about the specimen and associated (meta)data) e.g. label or tag, material: tag fading or falling off leading to loss of biological material identity) 	
Preservation /stabilization	PRESERVATION / STABILIZATION	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Preservation/stabilization method/procedure</u> (e.g. method, reagents, specimen size, volume ratio of specimen- to-preserved/stabilizer solution; temperature, duration) 	H
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Stabilization date/time</u> (time interval to collection) 	H
Inter-mediate storage/	STORAGE & TRANSPORT	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Intermediate storage/transport condition and duration</u> (e.g. method, duration, temperature, unintended temp. fluctuations, thawing or freezing; breaking/leakage; humidity/moisture; air) 	H
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Sample container(s) type ... same as above</u> (e.g., closure integrity, composition; material resistance to temp./chemicals, size (for holding sample & preservation solution) evaporation or spillage, breakage, leaking) 	□
Reception	RECEPTION	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Reception procedure, date/time, person</u> e.g. legal/regulatory and specimen quality requirements 	H
Sample processing	SAMPLE PROCESSING	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Sample processing method/procedure & condition</u> e.g. cleaning, sterilization, cutting, grinding or other homogenization etc., methods incl. reagents and equipment used, durations and temperature applied, specimens (single, pooled); aliquoting, labelling; time-point 	H
Storage of samples	STORAGE OF SAMPLES (long-term or short-term until e.g. analyte isolation or analysis).	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <u>Sample storage container type and labelling</u> (e.g. suitability for storage, information on label, robustness of label) 	

- **Storage method, condition and duration**
(e.g. temperature (RT, +4°, -80° or liquid nitrogen liquid or gas phase); temperature variations, humidity, light, time until further processing or analysis)

Analyte isolation or other pre-processing for analysis

ANALYTE ISOLATION (e.g. RNA, DNA, protein)

- **Analyte isolation method** e.g.
 - date/time,
 - type of kit/method or own protocol, deviations from instructions,
 - plant cell and microbial cell lysis technique,
 - plant analyte content (e.g. DNA),
 - inhibitory compounds & impurities (e.g. in plants like tree bark: polysaccharides, phenolic compounds, lignin, that disturb DNA, RNA, and protein extraction; e.g. in soil: polysaccharide, heavy metals, or humic substances, that can interfere with downstream applications such as PCR and RT-PCR.
 - contamination from kits/reagents/personnel/air;

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- **Contamination** (e.g. with microbiome cells or DNA (e.g. from other samples, by lab personnel, environment, equipment, reagents))

- **Analyte quantification and quality control method**
(e.g. type of method, buffers and equipment used)

- **Analyte storage method, condition and duration**
(e.g. temperature (RT, +4 °C, -80 °C or liquid nitrogen liquid or gas phase); temperature variations, humidity, light, time until further processing or analysis)

Legend:

H = highly relevant